

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_LSM_50x_natural_c_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 12:47:36 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	40.55	µm	
Size:	65531	digits	
Spacing:	0.6188	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\Dropbox\jmmarreir...0x_naural_c_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 12:47:36 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	16.71	μm	
Min:	-9.56	μm	
Max:	7.150	μm	
Size:	270047	digits	
Spacing:	0.06188	nm	
NM-points ratio:	18.75 % (1687820 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 12:47:36 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	16.71	μm	
Size:	270047	digits	
Spacing:	0.06188	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	2.766	μm	
Ssk	-0.4033		
Sku	3.098		
Sp	7.149	μm	
Sv	9.560	μm	
Sz	16.71	μm	
Sa	2.202	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.6746	%	
Smc	3.359	μm	
Sxp	6.337	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	29.18	μm	
Str	0.6230		
Std	157.5	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.5356		
Sdr	11.14	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.1043	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	3.463	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.1043	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	2.594	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	3.106	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.3573	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	8.061	µm
Mean depth of furrows	2.633	µm
Mean density of furrows	3280	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	180.0	°
Second direction	135.0	°
Third direction	45.01	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	85.46	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

